

Synthesis, structural, thermal characterization and antifungal studies of manganese(II), cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes with N, O donor ligands

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Abstract : The solid complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff bases derived from 3-acetyl-6-methyl-(2*H*)-pyran-2,4(3*H*)-dione (dehydroacetic acid) and 3-methoxy aniline and 3-amino toluene, have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, conductometry, thermal, magnetic, IR, NMR, UV-Vis spectral and X-ray powder diffraction studies. From the analytical data the stoichiometry of the complexes has been found to be 1 : 2 (metal : ligand). The low conductance values suggest that the complexes are non-electrolytes. IR spectral data suggest that the ligand behaves as a bidentate neutral with N : O donor. Thermal study indicates about the stability of complexes. The powder XRD suggests monoclinic crystal system for the complexes. The physico-chemical data indicates octahedral geometry for all the complexes. Complexes have been screened for antifungal activity against *A. niger*.

Keywords : Dehydroacetic acid, transition metal complexes, Schiff bases, thermal analysis, powder X-ray diffraction.

Introduction

Metal complexes of biologically important ligands are sometimes more effective than the free ligands¹. Schiff bases have a central role as chelating ligands in main group and transition metal coordination chemistry². They deserve proper attention because of their role in biological applications and excellent chelating ability^{3,4}. It is well known from the literature that dehydroacetic acid (3-acetyl-6-methylpyran-2,4-dione) (DHA) have a strong ability to form metal complexes. Besides its chelating ability, it also shows promising antifungal, antibacterial and antiprotozoal activities^{5,6}. In continuation with our earlier reported study⁷ we report here the preparation and characterization of complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions with new ligands, 3-[3-methoxy-phenyliminoethyl]-6-methyl-pyrane-2,4-dion (L1) and 3-[3-tolyliminoethyl]-6-methyl-pyrane-2,4-dion (L2), derived from condensation of DHA with 3-methoxy aniline and 3-amino toluene respectively which are not reported in literature.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are coloured solids, stable to air and non hygroscopic. They decompose at high tempera-

ture without melting. They are insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in common non-polar organic solvents. The molar conductance values 2.4 to 19.50 mho cm² mol⁻¹ for 10⁻⁴ M solution of metal complexes in DMF indicates that the metal complexes are non electrolyte in nature⁸. The elemental analysis indicates mononuclear nature and 1 : 2 composition of metal to ligand. The metal analyses by EDTA titration method are confirmed by atomic absorption spectroscopy. The analytical results of complexes are presented in Table 1.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands have been recorded in CDCl₃. The spectra of L1 shows sharp peaks at 2.19 (3H, s, pyran C6-CH₃), 5.78 (1H, s, pyran C5-H), 15.47 (1H, s, enolic OH for DHA moiety) and 2.56 (3H, s, CH₃-C=N), 3.81 (3H, s, CH₃ of methoxy group), the phenyl moiety values 6.98-7.36 (4H, m, Ar-H).

The ¹H NMR spectra of L2 shows sharp peaks at 2.17 (3H, s, pyran C6-CH₃), 5.77 (1H, s, pyrane C5-H), 15.47 (1H, s, enolic OH for DHA moiety), 2.40 (3H, s, CH₃-C=N) and 2.60 (3H, s, toluene CH₃). The phenyl moiety values 7.00-7.40 (4H, m, Ar-H).

Table 1. Analytical data of ligands and its complexes

Compd./ Complex	Color	Analysis (%) :					Mol. wt.	M.p./ Decomposition (°C)	λ_m (mho cm ² mol ⁻¹)
		Found (Calcd.)							
		C	H	N	Cl	M			
C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NO ₄ (L1)	White	65.16 (65.93)	5.12 (5.53)	4.94 (5.13)	-	-	273.29	108	
[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Cu] [1]	Violet	52.27 (52.91)	3.95 (4.44)	3.87 (4.11)	10.09 (10.41)	8.96 (9.33)	681.02	>270	4.4
[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Co] [2]	Light pink	52.87 (53.27)	4.15 (4.47)	3.94 (4.14)	10.00 (10.48)	8.26 (8.71)	674.41	>270	9.6
[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Mn] [3]	Dark brown	53.18 (53.59)	4.03 (4.50)	3.78 (4.17)	10.01 (10.55)	7.96 (8.17)	672.40	>270	19.5
C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NO ₃ (L2)	White	69.60 (70.02)	5.47 (5.88)	5.02 (5.44)	-	-	257.29	118	
[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ Cu] [4]	Dark brown	55.11 (55.52)	4.08 (4.66)	4.02 (4.32)	10.39 (10.93)	9.33 (9.79)	649.02	>270	4.9
[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ Co] [5]	Light green	55.81 (55.92)	4.40 (4.69)	4.27 (4.35)	10.85 (11.00)	8.83 (9.15)	644.41	224	19.1
[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ Mn] [6]	Dark brown	55.98 (56.26)	4.47 (4.72)	4.02 (4.37)	10.87 (11.07)	8.14 (8.58)	640.41	270	13.4

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of ligands L1 and L2 shows bands respectively at 3371 cm⁻¹ and 3368 cm⁻¹ for νOH (hydrogen bonded), 1714 cm⁻¹ and 1697 cm⁻¹ for νC=O (lactone), 1663 cm⁻¹ and 1649 cm⁻¹ for νC=N (azomethine), 1460 cm⁻¹ and 1428 cm⁻¹ for νC-N (aryl azomethine) and 1637 cm⁻¹ and 1629 cm⁻¹ for νC=O (enolic) vibrations. The IR spectrum of ligands supports their tautomeric nature⁹. In the IR spectra of metal chelates no band is observed in the region 3368–3371 cm⁻¹ indicating the absence of enolic form of ligand in complexes. Coordination is supported by downward shift by 17 to 29 cm⁻¹ in νC=N azomethine¹⁰ and 23–27 cm⁻¹ in νC=O enolic¹¹. The new bands appeared in the region 595–630 and 500–541 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to M-N and M-O bonds¹².

This indicates that the ligands behave as bidentate and coordinate to metal ions through enolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen.

Magnetic and electronic spectra :

The magnetic moments of Cu^{II} complexes are found at 1.95 B.M. and 1.85 B.M. for [1] and [4] complexes respectively. The electronic absorption spectra of Cu^{II} complexes show a broad band at 15106 cm⁻¹ and 15129 cm⁻¹ for [1] and [4] complexes respectively assignable to

${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. The band around 27933 cm⁻¹ and 28329 cm⁻¹ are due to charge transfer spectra respectively for complexes [1] and [4].

The magnetic moments of Co^{II} complexes are found 4.16 B.M. and 4.46 B.M. for complexes [2] and [5] respectively. The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes showed three absorption bands around 10004 cm⁻¹, 19305 cm⁻¹ and 22933 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively suggesting high spin octahedral geometry¹⁴.

The electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complexes show the absorption bands around 15152 cm⁻¹, 24691 cm⁻¹ and 31546 cm⁻¹. The first two band may be assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$, and third band may be assigned due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}(G)$ transition or charge transfer transition. The magnetic moment values for Mn^{II} complexes [3] and [6] are 5.53 B.M. and 6.00 B.M. respectively. These facts indicate that the complexes has octahedral geometry^{15–17}.

Thermal study :

The thermogram of Co^{II} complex with ligand L2 reveals that no weight loss occurs up to 250 °C. The rapid decomposition starts after 250 °C which is due to the decomposition of organic ligand and subsequent oxida-

tion which is indicated by large exotherm at ~ 295 °C. About 91% weight loss takes place up to 860 °C. Above this temperature weight remains almost stable up to 1000 °C indicates the formation of stable residue¹⁸.

X-Ray diffraction :

The X-ray powder diffraction of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes (L2) have been studied as representative systems. The observed 2θ with relative intensity more than 10% are indexed and have been used for evaluation. The Cu^{II} complex gives 7 reflections of 2θ between 7.78 to 28.79 with maximum $2\theta = 11.85$ and $d = 7.46$ Å are observed. The Co^{II} complex gives 11 reflections of 2θ between 8.85 to 28.53 with maximum $2\theta = 9.55$ and $d = 9.24$ Å are observed. The X-ray diffraction pattern of the complex with respect to their prominent peaks has been indexed by using computer software¹⁹. The above index method also yielded miller indices (h, k, l) values unit cell parameters, volume of unit cell and space group. The unit cell parameters for the given diffractogram of Cu^{II} are $a = 11.83926$ Å, $b = 22.69410$ Å and $c = 8.11671$ Å, with $\alpha = \gamma = 90.00^\circ$ and $\beta = 105.904^\circ$. The unit cell parameters for the given diffractogram of Co^{II} are $a = 18.67931$ Å, $b = 9.84437$ Å and $c = 13.10770$ Å, with $\alpha = \gamma = 90.00^\circ$ and $\beta = 98.178^\circ$. Both the samples are found to be monoclinic in nature with space group $P2_1/m$. The experimental density value of the complexes were determined by using specific gravity method²⁰, which is further used to calculate the volume of unit cell. The experimental density and theoretical density values are 1.789141 g cm⁻³ and 1.815466 g cm⁻³ respectively of Cu^{II} complexes and 1.41356 g cm⁻³ and 1.43215 g cm⁻³ respectively of Co^{II} complexes are found in good agreement and within the limits of experimental error. The other parameters such as porosity and particle size were calculated and are 1.432%, 312.2541 Å respectively for Cu^{II} complex and 1.298%, 246.37 Å respectively for Co^{II} complex. The number of molecules (n) per unit cell were calculated using equation $\rho = nm/NV$ and found 2 and 4 molecules per unit cell for Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes respectively.

Fungicidal activity :

The ligand and their corresponding metal chelates were screened by mycelial dry weight (MDW) method *in vitro* against *Aspergillus niger* for their fungicidal activity in

glucose nitrate (GN) media. Medium prepared by adding 10 g of glucose, 2.5 g of KNO₃, 1 g of KH₂PO₄ and 0.5 g of MgSO₄ in 1 liter of distilled water and the fungus was cultivated on GN media. The ligand and complexes under investigation were added to GN medium (200 ppm and 400 ppm) preparing solutions/suspension. The conical flask containing medium with ligand and complexes, autoclaved at 15 lbs for 30 min, inoculated with *A. niger*, after 168 h the mycelium obtained was collected by filtration through Whatman filter paper. The yield of MDW was recorded. The ligand exhibited toxicity in the inhibition. Due to synergistic combination of the coordinated metal ions with the ligands, the inhibition has been increased in complexes up to 85%. The order of inhibition with respect to metal ion is Co > Mn > Cu. The results are similar to the observations made by other workers^{21,22}.

where, M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}

Fig. 1

Conclusions :

From the above discussion proposed complexes have distorted octahedral geometry for the Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and octahedral geometry for Mn^{II} complexes. The ligand behaves as bidentate N, O donor coordinating through azomethine nitrogen and oxygen of enolic carbonyl group. The complexes are biologically active since they exhibit enhanced antifungal activities compared to their parent ligands. The thermal study of Co^{II} complex indicates that complexes are thermally stable. The XRD study suggests monoclinic $P2_1/m$ crystal system.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used in all preparative and analytical works were of A.R. grade. Dehydroacetic acid was obtained from Merck. The micro analytical data for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen content in each sample were recorded on Elemental Analyzer Perkin-Elmer model

no. 2400; IR spectra (nujol) in the range of 4000–450 cm^{-1} were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1b model no. C75430 (The elemental analysis and IR spectra are recorded at School of Chemical Sciences, Jalgaon University, Jalgaon and ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand were measured in CDCl_3 at Department of Chemistry, Pune University, Pune). The AAS (Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy), TGA-DTA and XRD were recorded on Perkin-Elmer PE-Analyst 300, Ta/SDT-2960 and Philips 3701/Philips 1701 respectively at USIC, Shivaji University, Kolhapur. The UV-Vis spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were done using a Gouy's balance at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. Molar conductivity was measured on a conductivity meter EQ-660 with a dip-type cell using 10^{-4} M solution of complexes in DMF.

Synthesis of ligand :

The ligands are synthesized by mixing equimolar solution of dehydroacetic acid and 3-methoxy aniline (L1) and 3-amino toluene (L2) in double distilled dry ethanol and refluxed the mixture on 1RML rotamental for 6 h. The content was cooled to room temperature. The solid obtained was separated, washed and recrystallised from ethanol. The purity of the ligand were checked by TLC, melting point, elemental analysis and characterized by IR and PMR.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

To a hot solution of the ligand (2 mmol) in (30 ml) methanol, the metal chloride (1 mmol) in (20 ml) methanol was added dropwise with stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained by adding 10% methanolic solution of ammonia. The complexes of different metals were precipitated at different pH. It was then refluxed for 2–4 h. The resulting metal complex was filtered in hot condition and washed with chloroform, methanol, petether (40–60 $^\circ\text{C}$) and dried over calcium chloride in vaccum desicators.

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